

RESPONSE OF FRP-STRENGTHENED SLENDER RC COLUMNS UNDER CYCLIC COMPRESSION

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Keywords: Circular columns, Slender columns, Strengthening, Cyclic loading, CFRP

ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study is to investigate the effect of cyclic loading on FRP-confined slender circular RC columns. For this purpose, a total of 6 circular slender RC columns of height 1200 mm and diameter 150 mm were cast; 3 of which were tested under monotonic whereas remaining three were tested under cyclic compressive loads. Out of the six specimens, two were the control specimens and other four were strengthened using two different CFRP-strengthening schemes. In the first strengthening scheme, the two columns were strengthened using a single layer of CFRP sheets with the fibers orientation in the hoop direction. In the second strengthening scheme, other two columns were strengthened using two layers of CFRP with fibers in longitudinal direction and one layer of CFRP fibers in the hoop direction. The hoop CFRP sheet was bonded over the longitudinal sheets to improve the anchorage of longitudinal fibers and reduce the likelihood of flexural debonding failures. The monotonic and cyclic compression tests were performed using Amsler compression testing machine under pinned end conditions and an axial load eccentricity of 25 mm. To apply cyclic loading, the specimens were first loaded from 0 to 80% of the monotonic peak load and then unloaded to zero. This loading-unloading cycle (0 to 80%) was then repeated 3 times, and then finally load was increased monotonically until failure. The load-deflection response of control and strengthened slender RC columns were plotted to study the success of FRP-strengthening on improving the strength and deformation capacity of slender RC columns. In slender columns, the effect of longitudinal FRP fibers in carrying the load in post-yielding stage was more significant than hoop FRP fibers. The test results also showed that FRP-strengthening of slender columns is equally effective in cyclic compression as in monotonic compression.

1 INTRODUCTION

Despite this fact that the studies on FRP-confined RC columns under cyclic compression are of particular interest in the seismic retrofitting of the columns, the available studies on FRP-confined cylinders and RC columns are mostly under monotonic compressive loading only [e.g. 1-5], and there is limited work on cyclic compression of FRP-strengthened RC columns. The results presented in a paper by Rodrigues and Silva [6] discusses RC columns strengthened with FRP jackets under axial cyclic compression. The study on strength and ductility were conducted on 27 circular columns with

750 mm height and 150 mm diameter. Both Carbon and Glass FRP were utilized and stirrup spacing was varied. It was concluded from the study that there is a possibility of the monotonic loading curves staying below the envelope of static cyclic loading. Another study by Ilki and Kumbasar [7] describes the concentric compression test results of CFRP-sheet jacketed concrete specimens with circular, square and rectangular cross-sections. In the experimental program, pre-damaged specimens and repeated compressive loads were considered along with undamaged specimens and monotonic compressive loads. The contribution of CFRP composite jackets to the compressive behavior of the specimens was evaluated quantitatively, in terms of strength, longitudinal and lateral deformability and energy dissipation. Simple analytical expressions were proposed for compressive strength and ultimate axial strain that are valid for CFRP jacketed concrete with circular, square and rectangular cross-sections. The analytical results obtained by the proposed expressions were in good agreement with the experimental data obtained in this study, as well as the experimental data available in literature. It was observed from this study that Pre-damage and/or repeated compressive loading did not cause any remarkable disadvantage on the behavior of the CFRP jacketed concrete specimens, except minor reductions of initial axial stiffness for the specimens that had pre-damage conditions. Lam et al. [8] carried out an experimental study on concrete cylinders of 152 mm in diameter and 305 mm in height wrapped with carbon FRP in which the following main conclusions for FRP-confined concrete under cyclic compression were provided: (a) loading-unloading cycles have little effect on the envelope curve of stress-strain responses; (b) repeated unloading/reloading cycles have a cumulative effect on the permanent strain and stress deterioration, so the uniqueness concept of cyclic stress-strain responses is invalid; and (c) the envelope curve, compressive strength and ultimate axial strain can be accurately predicted using Lam and Teng's stress-strain model for FRP-confined concrete under monotonic compression [9,10]. Shao et al. [11] presented a cyclic stress-strain model for FRP confined concrete based on his own limited test data. In a comparative study of existing models by De Lorenzis and Tefers [12], the minimum average absolute error in strength prediction over circular sections was more than 13.4% while in ductility prediction the error was more than 35% for FRP wrapped concrete. Rousakis et al. [13], through an experimental investigation studied the behavior of RC square 200×200×320 mm columns strengthened with FRP. Both monotonic as well as cyclic loading were implemented. The main conclusions drawn from this study indicated that the external FRP confinement can substantially increase strength and ductility of axially loaded concrete even in low confinement volumetric ratios and the repeated load–unload cycles of axial compressive load in each of the three distinct regions of FRP confined concrete response caused no appreciable decrease of strength, ductility or energy absorption of concrete.

Although the above studies have provided valuable experimental and numerical data, but these studies are limited to short columns only and therefore the research outputs cannot be as is applied for slender columns. The aim of the present study is to investigate the effect of cyclic loading on FRP-confined *slender* circular RC columns. The effect of cyclic loading was studied in terms of columns' ultimate strength and deformation capacity.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

In order to study the effectiveness of externally-bonded hoop and longitudinal Carbon FRP (CFRP) sheets in reducing the lateral deflections and improving the strength and deformation capacity of slender circular RC columns under monotonic and cyclic compression, a detailed experimental program was designed. A total of 6 circular slender RC columns of height 1200 mm and diameter 150 mm were cast; 3 of which were tested under monotonic whereas remaining three were tested under cyclic compressive loads. Out of the six specimens, two were the control specimens and other four were strengthened using two different CFRP-strengthening schemes. In the first strengthening scheme, the two columns were strengthened using a single layer of CFRP sheets with the fibers orientation in the hoop direction. In the second strengthening scheme, remaining two columns were strengthened using two layers of CFRP with fibers in longitudinal direction and one layer of CFRP fibers in the hoop direction. The longitudinal CFRP sheets were first externally bonded around the full column circumference and a hoop CFRP sheet was then bonded over the longitudinal sheets to improve the anchorage of longitudinal fibers and reduce the likelihood of flexural debonding failures. The

monotonic and cyclic compression tests were performed using Amsler compression testing machine under pinned end conditions and an axial load eccentricity of 25 mm. Figure 1 shows the reinforcement details of the RC columns tested in the present study. As shown in Fig. 1, the columns had 4- $\phi 8$ rebars as longitudinal reinforcement and $\phi 6 @ 100$ mm c/c as transverse reinforcement. The nomenclature and strengthening schemes used in the present experimental investigation are shown in Table 1.

Figure 1: Reinforcement of circular column specimens.

2.1 Slenderness Ratio of the Specimens

Using the expression kl_u/r , the slenderness ratios of circular columns was estimated as 32. Here, l_u is the unsupported height of the column; k is the effective length coefficient, taken unity for pinned ends and r is the radius of gyration of the cross section of RC column which is calculated using gross cross-sectional properties of concrete. A slenderness limit of $kl_u/r = 34 - 12(M_1/M_2) < 40$ is specified by ACI 318 [14] for RC columns. With single curvature bending and equal end moments (i.e. $M_1 = M_2$) the limit reduces to $kl_u/r = 22$ which indicates that the columns of the present study are slender.

Specimen designation [§]	Loading Pattern (%)	Loading Type	No. of CFRP layers	
			Hoop CFRP	Long. CFRP
CON-C-MO	0-F	Monotonic	0	0
STR1-C-MO	0-F	Monotonic	1	0
STR2-C-MO	0-F	Monotonic	1	2
CON-C-CY	0-80(3)-0-F	Cyclic	0	0
STR1-C-CY	0-80(3)-0-F	Cyclic	1	0
STR2-C-CY	0-80(3)-0-F	Cyclic	1	2

[§]CON: Control; C: Circular; MO: Monotonic; CY: Cyclic; STR1: Strengthening scheme #1; STR2: Strengthening scheme #2.

Table 1: Overview of the specimens (Test Matrix).

2.2 Material Properties and Specimen Preparation

All the columns were cast using single batch of ready mix concrete. PVC circular pipes were used as formwork for casting circular columns as shown in Fig. 2. Three 150×300 mm standard cylinders were also cast to obtain mean compressive strength of concrete (f_c'). The steel bars were obtained from the local market to use them as longitudinal and transverse reinforcements. In order to determine the mechanical properties of the CFRP sheets used, coupon samples were cut from the CFRP sheets. Three coupons were tested as per ASTM D3039M using INSTRON tensile testing machine with hydraulic grips. Each specimen was subjected to a gradually increasing uniaxial load until failure took place. The average mechanical properties obtained are reported in Table 2 along with the average properties of the mix and the rebars. After the casting, the columns were cured for the two subsequent weeks and then left as is to dry for two more weeks. Detailed casting procedures are outlined in Fig. 2.

a) PVC formwork for circular columns

b) Steel cage inside PVC formwork

c) Concrete being poured inside formwork

d) Columns leveled after pouring

Figure 2: Casting of the column specimens.

2.3 Test Procedure

All the column specimens were tested using Amsler compression testing machine under pinned end conditions and an axial load eccentricity of 25 mm (Fig. 3). The test setup was prepared for monotonic and cyclic compression tests. The monotonic compression tests were performed under a displacement control configuration (0.5 mm/min) with monotonically increasing displacements until failure. To apply cyclic loading, the specimens were first loaded from 0 to 80% of the monotonic peak load and then unloaded to zero. This loading-unloading cycle (0 to 80%) was then repeated 3 times, and then finally load was increased monotonically until failure. In the first three cycles, applied loading was Load controlled (at the rate of 1 kN/sec), whereas displacement controlled testing (at the rate of 0.5 mm/min) was followed for the last cycle until failure.

Parameter	Nominal Value
<i>Concrete and Steel</i>	
Average compressive strength of concrete, f'_c (MPa)	35.1
Yield strength of the longitudinal rebars, f_y (MPa)	420
Yield strength of the transverse rebars, f_{ys} (MPa)	275
Modulus of elasticity of rebars, E_s (GPa)	200
<i>CFRP Composite System</i>	
Type of FRP used	Unidirectional CFRP sheet
Elastic modulus of CFRP (in primary fibers direction)	77.3×10^3 MPa
Elastic modulus of CFRP (90° to the primary fibers)	40.6 MPa
Ultimate tensile strength of FRP	846 MPa
Fracture strain	1.1%
Thickness of each layer, t_f	1.0 mm

Table 2: Material Properties.

Figure 3: An instrumented column ready for testing.

3 DISCUSSION OF TEST RESULTS

This Section discusses the results obtained from testing of circular reinforced concrete slender columns under eccentric monotonic as well as cyclic loading. The effect of cyclic loading has been

compared with the results from monotonic loading on RC columns. Discussion of results also include effect of two CFRP strengthening schemes. The first scheme employs only hoop confinement whereas another scheme incorporates both hoop as well as longitudinal confinement.

3.1 Load-deflection ($P-\Delta$) response

Figures 4 and 5 show the applied load P versus mid-height lateral deflection response for the column specimens tested under monotonic and cyclic loading respectively. As shown in these figures, the stiffness of the specimen strengthened with STR2 scheme is highest as its slope with the horizontal is maximum compared to other specimens. This relatively higher flexural stiffness in STR2 specimen can be attributed to longitudinal fibers bonded to the concrete surface (before attaching the hoop CFRP sheets). Also these figures show that the $P-\Delta$ response nonlinear. There are two reasons for nonlinearity in $P-\Delta$ plots — the nonlinear material response and the lateral deflection due to the bending of column. Since the effect of nonlinear material behavior is small compared to bending effect, the flat portion in $P-\Delta$ plot should be mainly expected due to instability or buckling of the columns. The flat portion in $P-\Delta$ plot is observed for all strengthened columns.

These figures illustrate that the trend of increase in load carrying capacity and the deformation capacity is the same under cyclic loading as for monotonic loading. That is, the increase in the load carrying capacity and deformation capacity are maximum for STR2 specimens and minimum for control specimens. For STR1 specimens the two capacities are higher than control and smaller than STR2 specimens due to obvious reasons. This clearly illustrates that the loading scheme adopted for the cyclic compression, has no substantial ill effect on the column, and the proposed FRP-strengthening schemes for slender columns are equally effective in cyclic compression as in monotonic compression.

Figure 4: Load-deflection response for control and strengthened columns under monotonic loading.

Figure 5: Load-deflection response for control and strengthened columns under cyclic loading.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be drawn on the basis of the study presented herein:

1. CFRP hoop wraps provide confinement to concrete and lateral support to the longitudinal fibers and thus increase the strength of the slender RC columns. The outer hoop layer in slender columns also helps in reducing the chances of flexural debonding of inner longitudinal fibers from concrete.
2. The fibers of longitudinal CFRP laminate can contribute substantially to the load carrying capacity if they are laterally supported by hoop fibers.
3. The trend of increase in load carrying capacity and the deformation capacity are almost the same under cyclic loading as for monotonic loading. That is, the increase in the load carrying capacity and deformation capacity are maximum for STR2 specimens and minimum for control specimens. For STR1 specimens, the two capacities (load and deformation) are higher than control but smaller than STR2 specimens.
4. The slender columns strengthened with two additional layers of longitudinal CFRP exhibit much higher deformation capacity compared to specimens confined by only 1-layer of hoop CFRP sheets.
5. The present cyclic loading, adopted for the cyclic compression, has no substantial ill effect on the column, and the proposed FRP-strengthening schemes for slender columns is equally effective in cyclic compression as in monotonic compression.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This Project was funded by the National Plan for Science, Technology and Innovation (MAARIFAH), King Abdulaziz City for Science and Technology, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Award Number (13-ADV858-02).

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